



The focus of this report is to provide a comprehensive overview of the life cycle of a fish, from spawning to maturity. The report is organized into four main sections: Spawning, Embryo/Larval Phase, Settlement, and Symbiosis. Each section contains detailed information on the various stages and factors involved in the process.

